

Research Article

Efficacy of garlic extract and mancozeb against seed borne fungal pathogen of farmer saved sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) and groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) seeds {2010-2011}

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted in 2010-11 at Department of Plant Protection, Hamelmalo Agricultural College, Hamelmalo, Eritrea to determine the type of seed borne fungal pathogens associated with stored sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) and groundnut seeds (*Arachis hypogaea*). The sorghum and groundnut seeds were obtained from Hamelmalo farmers of Keren Sub-Zoba. Five fungal genera were identified to be growing on the seed samples. These were *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Aspergillus* sp, *Rhizopus* sp and *Colletotrichum graminicola*. All the five fungi occurred in the control seed sub-samples, whereas only three (*Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Rhizopus* sp.) of the five occurred in the sub-samples that were treated with different treatments. On evaluation of fungicides and garlic extracts against seed borne fungal pathogen of sorghum and groundnut. All treatments were evaluated through inhibition of seed germination test and mycelia weight. Among different treatments combinations T₂ (4 gm garlic/kg seed) was most effective which showed maximum seed germination in sorghum and groundnut i.e. 96.70% and 0.42 and 0.26 g mycelia weight respectively followed by T₄ (2 g garlic+2 g mancozeb per kg seed) and T₃ (2 g mancozeb per kg seed) and was effective than control.

Key words: Seed borne fungal pathogen, sorghum, groundnut, storage, mancozeb, garlic extracts, *In vitro* evaluation.

Introduction

Almost 90% of all the world's food crops are grown from seeds (Schwinn, 1994). Seed are widely distributed in national and international trade, and germplasm is also distributed and exchanged in the form of seeds in breeding programmes. Due to their high mobility, seeds are a highly effective means for disseminating plant pathogens over long distances. Numerous examples exist in agriculture literature for the international spread of land diseases as a result of the importation of seeds that were infected or contaminated with pathogens (Agarwal and Sinclair, 1996). Many of the diseases that cause reduced yields in sorghum have seed borne phases. Seed borne inoculums therefore, have severe implications for yield, seed production and distribution systems, trade, human nutrition and germplasm. The management of these pathogens during the seed-borne phase is considered to be the cheapest disease control strategy (Shenge, 2007). However, effective management can only be implemented effectively if the pathogens are correctly identified. It is in view of this that the current study aimed at detecting seed borne pathogens on farmer saved sorghum and groundnut seeds at Ona, Hamelmalo (Basherit), Wazentet and Feredarb, East Africa, Eritrea.

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) belongs to Poaceae family, Anchoyogonae, which is native in Africa in the south of Sahara desert, where several closely related wild species are found. Abyssinia is probably the center of the origin, and Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) is one of the world's major food legume crops. It was originated where the genus *Arachis* is widely distributed. The natural distribution of all the *Arachis* species is confined to Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, Bolivia and Uruguay, (Krapovichas *et al.* 1973). Groundnut is cultivated in over 80 countries from 40°N to 40°S in tropical and warm temperate regions of the world. In Eritrea, Sorghum is most important and widely grown cereal crop, especially in lowlands, while groundnut is restricted to Anseba region and some parts of Gash Barka. Sorghum ranks first in the contribution towards national economy and diet and on an average 45% of the bulk total food production for the nation comes from it. Common groundnut products include oil, roasted food, salt seed, and peanut butter (Locally called Fofa).

In Anseba region till 2001 the area cultivated under sorghum and groundnut was about 20,178 hectares with a production of about 8442.1 tones (Anon, 2002). Fungi are one of the factors in storage seeds which reduce seed viability. Natural toxicants from plants have been used for pest control more than any other chemicals until recent past. Flowers, cloves, leaves, bark, root and seed extracts were used for pest control. Onion, garlic and ginger are most important botanical pesticides which are more effective and easily available as compared to synthetic pesticides. Garlic due to presence of diallyl sulfide and triallyl sulfide shows fungicidal property against seed borne fungus. Garlic extract spray has a broad spectrum effect (Olkowski *et al*; 1995).

Mancozeb belongs to thiocarbamates fungicides containing Magnese and Zinc, basically it is ethylene bisdithiocarbamates. It was included in the list of fungicides in 1950. It is very effective against seed borne diseases specially blight, seed rot, damping off, wilt etc. Mancozeb has a very low acute toxicity to mammals. No toxicological effects were observed in a long term study with rats fed doses of 5 mg/kg (Hayes and Laws; 1990). The major routes of exposure to mancozeb are through the skin or from inhalation.

Materials and methods

Experimental location

The laboratory experiment was conducted in 2010-11 at the Laboratory of the Department of Plant Protection, Hamelmalo Agricultural College, Hamelmalo.

Sources of experimental materials

Ten samples of sorghum and groundnuts seeds collected from sorghum and groundnut growing areas of Hamelmalo were used for the identification of seed-borne fungi, seed germination percentage and mycelia weight of fungus.

Fungicides used

(a) Garlic extracts (botanical fungicides), (b) Mancozeb (chemical fungicides)

Cleaning and sterilization of glassware's: The glasswares were properly washed, dried and surface sterilization with 70% ethyl alcohol.

Preparation and application of the garlic extracts and mancozeb: 2g/kg seed of garlic clove weighing 2 g garlic clove and grinded it and mixed with 10 ml water (w/v 16.67%). Same procedure is adopted for 4 g garlic clove (w/v 28.57%). Adjuvant like 1 % jiggery (glue) and a pinch of robin blue were added as sticking agents. Seed dressed with 2g mancozeb (80% wp) per kg seed of groundnut and sorghum (80% wettable powder)

Seed germination: The Standard blotter method was developed by Doyer in 1938 which was later included in the International Seed Testing Association Rules of 1966. 10 and 5 seeds of each sorghum and groundnut respectively were tested by employing standard blotter method in three replications for each treatment. Two discs of blotting paper of 90 mm size were moistened with distilled water and placed in 90 mm surface sterilized Petriplates after draining excess water. Seeds were placed at equal distance in each Petriplate. The plates were incubated at 25 ± 2 °C under darkness.

Sampling for germination was done at 72 h (3 days) after incubation, while identification of sporulating fungi was done at 7 days. The Petridishes were brought to the examination area in the laboratory, where each seed was examined under a microscope. Growth habits of the various fungi growing in the Petriplates were observed carefully. Slide preparations of the various fruiting structures of the fungi were made and observed under a microscope for identification. The various types of fungi were identified using identification keys and cross-checked for each seed plated to identify the type of fungus growing on each seed. Standard book and papers were consulted while the examination of these fungi (Aneja, 2004; Rifai, 1969 and Barnet and Hunter, 1972).

Seed germination percentage = $\left\{ \frac{\text{Total number of germinated seeds}}{\text{total number of seeds}} \right\} \times 100$

The treatments were as follows:

1. Control (T₀)
2. Two grams of garlic extract (w/v 16.67%) / kg seed (T₁)
3. Four grams of garlic extract (w/v 28.57%) / kg seed (T₂)
4. Two grams of mancozeb (80%w.p / kg seed (T₃)
5. T₄ = [T₁ (Two grams of garlic extract (w/v 16.67%)) + T₃ (Two grams of mancozeb (80%w.p)) / kg. seed

Experimental Design: The experiment was conducted in laboratory of plant protection in Hamelmalo Agricultural College from February 24 to April 21, 2011. Design of the experiment was Complete Randomized Design having five (5) treatments and three (3) replications. Analysis of variance method was applied for drawing conclusion from the data. The calculated value was compared with tabulated value at 1% level of probability (Fisher and Yates, 1968) for the appropriate degree of freedom (d.f.).

Results and Discussion

The seed samples of sorghum and groundnut collected from different parts of Hamelmalo were tested initially, by employing Standard blotter method as described in 'Material and Methods' and the results are presented in Table 1 and Plate 1. Totally, five fungi were encountered. The results of this study indicated the dominance of *Alternaria*, *Fusarium* and *Colletotrichum*.

Table 1: Mycoflora associated with sorghum and groundnut seeds in seed health testing of different samples collected from different parts of Hamelmalo by Standard Blotter Method.

Name of fungi	Sorghum	Groundnut	Species
<i>Alternaria</i>	+	-	<i>alternata</i>
<i>Fusarium</i>	+	+	<i>oxysporum</i>
<i>Aspergillus</i>	+	+	<i>niger</i>
<i>Rhizopus</i>	+	-	
<i>Colletotrichum</i>	+	-	<i>graminicola</i>

Identification of fungi

The identification of above fungi was done based on the morphological and colony characters (Aneja, 2004, Barnet and Hunter, 1972 Ellis., 1971, and Rifai, 1969). Species of *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, *Colletotrichum*, *Rhizopus* and *Aspergillus* were identified at Laboratory of Plant Protection, Hamelmalo Agricultural College, Hamelmalo, Eritrea. Five fungi were noticed in sorghum and groundnut seed samples collected from Hamelmalo areas of Keren. Among them, viz. *Alternaria alternata* and *Fusarium oxysporum* have often appeared in many samples along with species of *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus* and *Colletotrichum graminicola*. Spore morphology and colony characters are given below.

***Alternaria alternata*:** The fungus produces wooly or powdery chains of dark brown conidia of variable lengths and shapes. The color of the colony is usually extremely variable between olive green to dark brown. On incubated seed, the fungus produced wooly or powdery chains of dark brown conidia of variable lengths and shapes. Hyphae are dark brown, thick, septate and branched. Conidiophores are simple, erect, thick and often clustered. The chains normally branch at the beak of a spore. Conidia have 4-5 transverse and 5-6 longitudinal septa; and are ovoid to obovoid, obclavate, obpyriform, ellipsoidal, muriform, with an elongated terminal cell.

***Aspergillus niger*:** Colony of *Aspergillus* on seed is usually spreading and very light yellow to deep yellow-green, olive brown. Masses of yellow-green ball-like structures supported on stalks are visible on dry incubated seeds under a stereo binocular microscope. On incubated seed, the fungus produces compact globose to radiate conidial heads in shades of green. Conidiophores of the fungus stand erect on the seed. They are simple, unbranched, colorless, transparent, and smooth.

***Rhizopus* spp.:** *Rhizopus* spp. is a common contaminant on seed. Colony of *Rhizopus* on the seed spreads rapidly by means of stolons with abundant, loose, gray mycelium. Colonies of *Rhizopus* grow very rapidly, fill the Petri dish, and mature in 4 days. The texture is typically cotton candy like. From the front, the color of the colony is white initially and turns grey to yellowish brown in time. Nonseptate or sparsely septate broad hyphae, sporangiophores, rhizoids (root-like hyphae), sporangia, and sporangiospores are visualized.

***Fusarium oxysporum*:** Here the species are convex shaped. Septation is in transverse form. Micro and macro conidia present with two or three septation. The hyphae are intermingled at their bases. Conidiophores are distinct in structure carrying the conidia, which functions for the production of sporodochium and synnema.

***Colletotrichum graminicola*:** Like that of the *Aspergillus* species, conidium of these genera is made of one cell. They are consisting of spores having light color. The conidia here unlike that of the other genera with in a structure called acervuli.

Table 2: Effect of garlic extract and mancozeb on seed germination percentage

Treatment	Sorghum Seed germination %	Groundnut Seed germination %
T ₀ (control)	76.7	83.33
T ₁ (Two grams of garlic extract (w/v 16.67%) / kg seed)	93.33	86.70
T ₂ (Four grams of garlic extract (w/v 28.57%) / kg seed)	96.70 a	96.70 a
T ₃ (Two grams of mancozeb (80%w.p / kg seed)	93.33	93.33
T ₄ (T ₁ +T ₃)	93.33	93.33
Grand Mean	6.32 b	8.69 b
LSD (1%)	14.09	12.37
c.v%	8.5	11.7

The values of germination percentages are arc sin transformation values necessary for statistical calculation

In general there is highly significance among the treatment when it is compared by LSD. The treatments (T₁, T₂, T₃, and T₄) do not show difference among each other. However; all these treatments are significant difference from the control. From the five treatments T₂ has got high mean value which is 96.7 where as the lowest mean value is from T₀ i.e. 76.7 in case sorghum (Table 2). Similarly there is also high significance among the treatment (T₂, T₃, and T₄) in case of groundnut but there is significant difference between (T₀ and other treatments) except T₁. Here T₂ have got the highest mean value i.e. 96.7 (Table 2).

Table 3: Effect of garlic extract and mancozeb on mycelial weight (in gram) of seed borne fungal pathogen of sorghum and groundnut.

Treatments	Sorghum Mycelial Weight (g)	Groundnut Mycelial Weight (g)
T ₀ (control)	1.054 a	0.778 a
T ₁ (Two grams of garlic extract (w/v 16.67%) / kg seed)	0.858 b	0.517 b
T ₂ (Four grams of garlic extract (w/v 28.57%) / kg seed)	0.770 b	0.407 b
T ₃ (Two grams of mancozeb (80%w.p / kg seed)	0.888 b	0.432 b
T ₄ (T ₁ +T ₃)	0.707 b	0.587 c
Grand Mean	0.856	0.544
LSD (1%)	0.1653	0.1636
c.v%	13.8	13.1

In case of sorghum from the analysis of variance, the treatments (T₁, T₂, T₃, and T₄) show high significant difference when compared with the control. But they do not show any significant difference among each other in case of sorghum. Here the highest mycelial weight is obtained from T₀ (1.054 g) and the lowest from T₄ (0.707g) (Table-3).

Where in case of groundnut, the treatments (T_1 , T_2 , T_3 , and T_4) show high significant difference compared with the control, but here we have also T_4 showing significant difference from T_1 , T_2 and T_3 . The highest and the lowest mycelial weight have been obtained in T_0 (0.778 g) and T_2 (0.407 g) respectively (Table3). Studies on the effect of seed-borne infections of sorghum and groundnut on germination, mycelia weight and seed borne pathogen revealed that seed germination decreased 23.3 to 3.3 % in different treatments with the increase in mycelia weight 0.42 to 0.59g in case of sorghum while in case of groundnut seed germination decreased 16.67 to 3.3 % in different treatments with the increase in mycelia weight 0.26 to 0.42 g. Loss in germination to the extent of 27 to 33 per cent was noticed. Sorghum and groundnut recorded germination of 96.67% in T_2 treatments (garlic extract 4g/kg seed). Control seed samples exhibited significantly more mycelia weight as compared to treated seeds. This effect may probably due to seed-borne fungus like *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Rhizopus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Colletotrichum graminicola* which is known to produce some toxins, which may be detrimental to seed germination. The fact that more of the fungal pathogens identified were detected on the control sorghum and groundnut seeds suggests that such fungi could be surface contaminants. This further highlights the need for seed treatment as a strategy for managing the pathogens. Seed treatment is considered to be a cheap and highly effective means of managing seed-borne diseases in crops (Shenge, 2007). Similar findings of loss in seed germination percentage and mycelial weight by *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, *Rhizopus*, *Aspergillus* and *Colletotrichum* were reported by Agarwal and Sinclair (1997), Abdurahman (2005), Javid *et al.* (2006), Masum *et al.*, (2008), Mesta *et al.* (2009), Rathod *et.al.*, (2010).

Summary and conclusion

The present investigation was undertaken during the period 2010-11 at the Department of Plant Protection, Hamelmalo Agricultural College, Hamelmalo, Eritrea which included testing of sorghum and groundnut seed samples for seed-borne mycoflora, evaluation of seed health testing methods, effect of seed mycoflora on germination, management of seed borne pathogen of sorghum and groundnut and management of seed mycoflora of sorghum and groundnut in storage. The results obtained are summarized hereunder. Seed health testing of different sorghum and groundnut seed samples collected from different parts of Hamelmalo revealed the dominance of *Alternaria alternata* followed by *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Colletotrichum graminicola*. Other saprophytic fungi included *Aspergillus niger* and species of *Rhizopus*. Of the thirty sorghum and groundnut seed samples tested, showed maximum seed-borne infection between 21-64% among seed samples of sorghum and groundnut crops tested from different farmers, showed maximum infection of *A. alternata* and *F. oxysporum*. Studies on the effect of seed-borne infections of sorghum and groundnut on seed germination indicated that there was reduction in germination with the increase in the seed infection by various fungi. The germination percentage of Sorghum and Groundnut was taken. The highest percentage of both the crops was obtained in T_2 followed by T_3 and the lowest was seen in T_0 . However, all the four treatments, except control, showed high germination percentage.

With regard to the mycelial weight, T_0 has the highest (1.054 g) and the lowest was in T_4 (0.707) in case of sorghum. While in Groundnut T_0 showed the highest mycelial weight (0.778) where as the lowest was in T_2 (0.407). Since all the treatments, except the control, showed similar results in the experiment conducted, thus, both (Garlic extract and Mancozeb) found to be effective for the control purpose. According to the cost-benefit analysis, it is better for the farmer to use garlic extract than mancozeb as seed dressing.

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